

Treatment of the epoxide (2) with BBr₃. Formation of taraxa-21-oxo-3β-yl acetate (7): The epoxide (2; 0.1 g) was treated with BBr₃ (0.2 ml) in dry benzene (15 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The usual work up furnished a solid (7), m.p. 290–92° [α]_D+102° (CHCl₃).

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-IX†. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-5-*p*-(2',4'-bis-ethylamino-s-triazin-6'-ylaminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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SOME s-triazazine and 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have found important biological application^{1,2}. With a view to get better therapeutic activity, we have synthesised³ compounds of type 4 containing

† Part-VIII; See Ref. 8.

both the said moieties and screened them for their antimicrobial activity.

Cyanuric chloride¹ (0.1 mol, 18.4 g) was condensed with ethylamine (0.2 mol, 9.8 g) to get 2,4-bis-ethylamino-6-chloro-s-triazazine (1). The third chlorine atom of cyanuric chloride was replaced by ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate to get the triazine (2) which was further treated with hydrazine hydrate to obtain the hydrazide (3). The hydrazide (3) was then condensed with different aromatic acids in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride to obtain the 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (4). The structure of the products has been characterised by ir spectral study.

- 1; X=Cl
2; X=NHC₆H₄CO₂Et (*p*)
3; X=NHC₆H₄CONHNH₂ (*p*)

4

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method⁴. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 μg using gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *Escherichia coli* and *Marcasane serratia*, and fungi, i.e. *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. It was observed that most of the compounds were moderately active (16–24 mm zone of inhibition) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

However, comparatively significant activity was observed in compounds bearing (in parenthesis zone of inhibition, mm) R=phenyl (15–19), styryl (14–24), 3-chlorophenyl (14–23), 3-hydroxyphenyl (15–20), 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl (13–24) and 3-pyridinyl (14–19).

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) was taken on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–400 cm⁻¹.

Ethyl(2,4-bis-ethylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)aminobenzoate (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol, 2.02 g) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.01 mol, 1.7 g) in dioxane (10 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from dioxane,

(73%), m. p. 148° (Found: C, 58.03; H, 6.45; N, 25.16. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O_2$ calcd. for: C, 58.18; H, 6.66; N, 25.45%).

p-(2,4-Bis-ethylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)aminobenzoyl hydrazide (3):

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol, 3.3 g) in dioxane (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol, 0.52 g) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The product (3) was collected by filtration and crystallised from dioxane, (78%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 53.00; H, 6.28; N, 35.08. $C_{14}H_{20}N_8O$ calcd. for: C, 53.16; H, 6.32; N, 35.44%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 (NH str.), 1690 (C=O str.), 720 (NH wag) and 820 cm^{-1} (C_3N_3 ring skeleton).

2-Phenyl-5-*p*-(2',4'-bisethylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4; R=Ph): Benzoic acid (0.05 mol, 0.61 g) was condensed with the hydrazide (3; 0.05 mol 1.58 g) in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride (0.05 mol) and refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath. The contents were poured in water and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was filtered off and crystallised from dioxane, (62%), m.p. 58° (Found: C, 62.49; H, 5.48; N, 27.73. $C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$ calcd. for: C, 62.68; H, 5.47; N, 27.86%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3350 (NH str.), 1600 (C=N str.), 1170 (C-O-C str. ether linkage) and 830 cm^{-1} (C_3N_3 ring moiety).

Similarly, other substituted-oxadiazoles (4) were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-5-*p*-(2',4'-DIETHYLAMINO-S-TRIAZIN-6'-YLAMINO-PHENYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (4)

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	N % : Found/Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	58	27.73 (27.66)
2.	2-Aminophenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	184	29.93 (30.21)
3.	3-Aminophenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	135	30.00 (30.21)
4.	4-Aminophenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	235	30.06 (30.21)
5.	Styryl	$C_{23}H_{24}N_8O$	76	25.78 (26.16)
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}ClN_8O$	78	25.12 (25.68)
7.	3-Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}ClN_8O$	69	25.00 (25.68)
8.	4-Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}ClN_8O$	150	24.33 (25.68)
9.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	128	25.93 (26.79)
10.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	172	25.48 (26.79)
11.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	73	26.00 (26.79)
12.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	193	24.32 (25.80)
13.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	158	23.96 (25.80)
14.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	218	24.68 (25.80)
15.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	169	23.96 (24.88)

(Table 1 contd.)

16.	2-Acetoxyphenyl	$C_{13}H_{14}N_2O_3$	122	24.12 (24.34)
17.	Benzoylaminoethyl	$C_{13}H_{14}N_2O_2$	154	27.10 (27.45)
18.	Benzyl	$C_{13}H_{14}N_2O$	73	25.13 (26.92)
19.	4-Nitrophenyl	$C_{11}H_{11}N_2O_2$	104	28.03 (28.18)
20.	3-Pyridinyl	$C_{10}H_{11}N_2O$	161	30.78 (31.26)
21.	4-Pyridinyl	$C_{10}H_{11}N_2O$	164	29.98 (31.26)

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) with Oxime, Semicarbazone and Thiosemicarbazone of 3-Methoxysalicylaldehyde

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PRESENT communication deals with complexation behaviour of Fe^{III} with oxime, semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone of 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde (*o*-vanillin) with a view to determining suitability of these reagents for the estimation of iron by spectrophotometric method.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. Ferric perchlorate was prepared from freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide by dissolving it in a minimum amount of perchloric acid. Iron content of the solution was estimated gravimetrically. A $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M Fe^{III}$ solution was prepared by appropriate dilution. Oxime, semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone of *o*-vanillin (EGA Chemie, W.